

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

The range of Xist transcriptional targets in human breast cancer neutralized by CDK4/6 inhibition.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

For this study we identified a set of 100 transcriptional targets of Xist in human breast cancer using primary tumor models and validated these genes as differentially expressed gene products in Xist-expressing breast cancer cells. We then used in vitro models of CDK4/6 small molecule inhibition in breast cancer cells (with and without exposure to palbociclib) to qualitatively and quantitatively characterize neutralization of Xist targets in breast cancer cells by pharmacologic inhibition of CDK4/6 with the -ciclib family of drugs (palbociclib, ribociclib, and abemaciclib).